

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Using more complex cover crop mixtures may lead to increased plant-available nitrogen in soil during the cropping season

Organic growers feed their soils and crops with organic inputs. Cover crops play an important role by capturing nitrogen and carbon and stimulating soil life with root exudates. By combining plant species, we potentially also combine the individual strengths. Can more complex mixes as intercrops provide higher nitrogen availability in the soil for the main crops? In a field trial conducted over 4 consecutive years, 4 different cover crop mixes were compared:

1. Phacelia and Black Oat: A standard without legumes.
2. Phacelia and Egyptian Clover: A legume + non-legume.
3. 5-Species Mix: A moderately diverse mix including legumes.
4. 12-Species Mix: A highly diverse mix including legumes.

This comparison took place on an organic managed plot, where non-inversion tillage has been employed for several years and

fertilisation happened with cattle farmyard manure. Only in Season 2 no fertiliser was applied (Season 1: 227 kg Ntot/ha manure + 50 kg Ntot/ha fertilizer pellets, Season 3: 239 kg Ntot/ha manure and Season 4: 158 kg Ntot/ha manure). Throughout the years (Season 1: broccoli, Season 2: red beet, Season 3: potato and Season 4: leek), the evolution of plant-available nitrate nitrogen in the 0-90 cm soil layer was measured.

Interestingly, there was a trend towards increased availability during the main cropping periods when the species-rich mixes (5-and 12-) including legumes were used. Since the observed differences were mostly trends and not statistically significant (except in 2021), further research is needed to confirm these results.

1. The evolution of plant-available nitrate nitrogen in the 0-90 cm soil layer (kg/ha) over the four trial years as a function of the choice of cover crop mixture (Inagro).

KEYWORDS

Cover crops, organic agriculture, plant available nitrogen

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